

Dellingr Phase 2: DO7

Nordic HPC/Cloud Inventory

Dellingr team *

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*Mathias Brännvall mathias.brannvall@it.uu.se; Juha Fagerholm juha.fagerholm@csc.fi; Jens Svalgaard Kohrt svalgaard@sdu.dk; Ivar Koppel ivar.koppel@ut.ee; Bjørn Lindi bjorn.lindi@ntnu.no; Ilja Livenson ilja.livenson@ut.ee; Petri Nikunen petri.nikunen@csc.fi; Anders Sjöström Anders.Sjostrom@lunarc.lu.se; Máni Maríus Viðarsson mani@hi.is; John White john.white@cern.ch;

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1 Executive Summary

This delivery is the first part of Dellingr DO7: An overview of the national HPC and Cloud resources available in each of the countries participating in Dellingr.

2 Dellingr Overview Scope

An important part of creating the overview is to establish what we consider to be a Cloud/HPC resource. Two criteria are important. The idea of both criteria is that we only want resources which *could* be part of the Dellingr resource sharing system to be part of the overview.

Resource Access

The resources must be accessible to users from other entities than where the resource is located. Many universities have HPC/Cloud installations which are only accessible within the university or in some cases even only accessible within a single research group.

The survey only considers installations which are accessible to users outside the entity where the resource is located. In principle the resource must be accessible by any academic researcher from the country. The resource may or may not be accessible to industry users and/or non-academic researchers from, e.g., state-owned institutions.

By accessible we mean that any applicable researcher within the country can get access to the resource by applying to a research council or similar entity. Access must be provided free-of-charge.

Resource Type

The resources should be able to run a variety of applications in a automatic way. We do not cover HPC or cloud installations which are small and/or could be characterized as single-user / single-purpose systems.

For HPC installations, there must be a scheduling system (Slurm, Moab, etc.) which enables users to submit jobs. For Cloud resources, users must be able to create new (virtual) machines in an at-least-almost automatic way.

To ensure more consistent numbers the overview should be done with the resources as of November 1, 2018.

Note that we do *not* consider the size of HPC and Cloud *investments* in each country, only the sizes of the actual resources available. This is due to the fact that it is very hard to get consistent monetary figures that can be compared between the countries. The accessible numbers for each

country usually always include the direct costs related to buying HPC/Cloud hardware, but may or may not include infrastructure costs (cooling/building), the cost of actually running it (electricity), system administrators, user support, etc.

3 National HPC and Cloud Infrastructures

The national HPC/Cloud infrastructures are implemented differently across the Nordics ranging from distributed per-university to more more centralized, national solutions.

For each country, this section gives give a short overview of how the general setup is done at the national level as defined in Section 2.

The following items should be covered.

- National player, corporate form, governance
- National and local HPC
- Access for researchers on HPC - how do you get access
- User support

3.1 Denmark – DeIC

DeIC is funded as part of the state budget. The board of DeIC is appointed by the Danish Agency for Science, Technology and Innovation after recommendations from Universities Denmark, the Free Research Council and the Strategic Research Council.

In this context, DeIC has in recent years partially sponsored two large Danish HPC/Cloud installations: DeIC National HPC Centre, SDU (Abacus 2.0) and DeIC National LifeScience Supercomputer (Computerome). Computerome also includes a cloud infrastructure. Both only give access to researchers by payment of a service fee per used/allocated core hour. For details, see Computerome resp. Abacus 2.0.

As the resources are only available by payment they are outside the scope of this overview (Section 2) and will not be counted in the table in Section 4. This of course does not mean that Danish research groups do not have access to any HPC resources but only that Danish funding system first require researchers to apply elsewhere for funding which they then can use either at the two nation wide HPC/Cloud installations or for a locally bought installation.

Both sites give basic user support. At Abacus 2.0, users at other universities than SDU in some cases get additional support from system administrators at their local university.

3.2 Estonia

Most hardware in Estonian compute infrastructure has been purchased by using structural funds. The daily operating costs are covered by universities, and in case of University of Tartu also by end-users. The faculties contribute to HPC budget based on the previous year's usage. All participating centers provide at least 5 percent of capacity for sharing in practice the share is up to 1/3. R D companies and private users can purchase resources commercially.

3.3 Finland – CSC

The national resources for computational science in Finland are provided by CSC – IT Center for Science, which is a limited non-profit company owned by the state (70%) and higher education institutions (universities and universities of applied sciences, 30%). Most resources are based on a contract with the Ministry of Education and Culture and they can be used by higher education institutions and state research institutes for non-private research and education.

Relatively large amount of Finnish resources are provided as cloud resources. This tells more of a shortage in HPC resources than a high availability of cloud resources. Both resource types are increased as time goes by, but HPC resources are acquired less often. The procurement for new HPC and cloud infrastructure is underway. On November 1, 2018, CSC had 57,128 cores in HPC systems Taito and Sisu. This corresponds to theoretical performance of 2,225 TFLOP. Cloud systems ePouta and ePouta had 15,240 cores. Storage systems for HPC and cloud systems had a raw capacity of 4000 TB and 5000 TB, respectively. More details about CSC's computing servers can be found [here](#).

Researchers can register as users with their HAKA identity or without it if their institution does not belong to the HAKA identity federation. You will get resources for basic use only by registering as a user.

Medium-scale resources are allocated by CSC's Resource Allocation Group and large-scale resources by the Scientific Customer Panel consisting of professors in computational and data science. The Resource Allocation Group has meetings usually every three weeks.

CSC gives support to users on both basic use and expert support on software. CSC has an extensive list of supported scientific software. Many courses are arranged to help users to utilize the resources.

3.4 Norway – Uninett Sigma2

UNINETT Sigma2 AS is responsible for the procurement, operation and further development of the generic national e-infrastructure for high-performance computing (HPC) and research data storage in Norway. The mandate, as well as funding, is given by the Research Council of Norway, in partnership with Norway's four oldest universities, the University of Bergen (UiB), the University of Oslo (UiO),

the University of Tromsø (UiT) and the Norwegian University of Science and Technology (NTNU) in Trondheim.

Through close cooperation with the partner universities, Sigma2 offers HPC and research data storage services to Norwegian universities and university colleges as well as to other publicly funded research organisations. Sigma2 also represents and coordinates Norway's participation in international collaborations on e-infrastructure, such as the Nordic e-Infrastructure Collaboration (NeIC), the Partnership for Advanced Computing in Europe (PRACE) and the European Data Infrastructure (EUDAT).

Sigma2 operates non-commercially although formally constructed as a company and a subsidiary of UNINETT AS. Sigma2 is headquartered in Trondheim.

Note that Norway is currently participating in the Dellingr project as an observer.

3.5 Iceland

Hardware in the Icelandic HPC centre (IHPC), which is more a concept than a company, was acquired with grants from the Icelandic Centre for Research along with contributions from the University of Iceland and Reykjavík University. The centre is run by the University of Iceland. Access is granted by sending an application (per account application not per project) to the IT department at the University of Iceland via email. Eligible users include users from Icelandic universities and projects funded by Icelandic Centre for Research. All usage is free to the end-users. Due to size and manpower user application support is limited.

3.6 Sweden – SNIC

The Swedish National Infrastructure for Computing (SNIC) is a national research infrastructure that provides compute/storage resources and user support to meet the needs of researchers from all scientific disciplines and from all over Sweden (universities, university colleges, research institutes, etc).

SNIC is a consortium between 10 Swedish universities and is funded by the Swedish Research Council and the consortium members. Uppsala University is the host organization of SNIC. It is the SNIC general assembly who propose members for the board of SNIC, which is then formally appointed by the Uppsala University's vice-chancellor.

There are six universities which hosts SNIC's compute/storage resources and provides system support. The consortia members also contribute with application experts for the users of the resources.

Access to the compute resources is granted for researchers from Swedish academia, all from small

(<5,000 ch/month) to large projects¹ (>100,000 ch/month). Smaller projects are applied for locally at any of the six SNIC centres, and PhD students and higher are eligible to apply. The larger projects undergo scientific evaluation before any resources are allocated and the PI must be assistant professors or higher to be eligible to apply. Calls for the large project are issued twice a year.

The six SNIC centres provide various HPC resources. SNIC Science Cloud is distributed across three of them. The centres have some level of specialization to distinguish between them, e.g. bioinformatics or visualization. SNIC keeps a list of available resources: <http://www.snic.se/resources>.

4 National HPC and Cloud Infrastructures

For each country, the following table summaries the available resources as defined in the previous sections. For Denmark, the numbers are all zero as discussed in Subsection 3.1.

	HPC TFLOP	HPC TB	Cloud cores	Cloud TB	Valid date
Denmark	0	0	0	0	Nov 2018
Estonia	950	4,500	3,000	300	Nov 2018
Finland	2,225	4,000	15,240	5,000	Nov 2018
Norway	2,000	6,000	256	6,000	Nov 2018
Iceland	175	0.1	0	0	Nov 2018
Sweden	5,766	ca 20,000	1,688	ca 250	Nov 2018

Legend

HPC / TFLOP and TB

National HPC compute power (theoretical teraflops) and storage available. For GPUs, we consider double precision flops.

Cloud / cores and TB

National cloud compute power (number of cores) and storage available.

¹The size of a large project is dependent on the size of the resource applied for and varies from >100kch/month to >200kch/month.

Valid date

Last date that a national total was updated.

5 Summary

The overview was done for the state in the Nordic countries as of November 1, 2018.

Note that for each country, the data does not necessarily include/count exactly the same as for the other countries.

Even with this in mind, it is clear that the nationally, freely available HPC/Cloud infrastructure in Norway, Finland, and in particular Sweden are a magnitude larger than Estonia and Iceland. Denmark has no freely available resources due to a different way to fund the infrastructure.

Appendix A Author Information

Name	email address	ORCID
Mathias Brännvall	mathias.brannvall@it.uu.se;	0000-0003-4979-4123
Juha Fagerholm	juha.fagerholm@csc.fi	0000-0002-9972-4468
Jens Svalgaard Kohrt	svalgaard@sdu.dk	0000-0002-3104-0406
Ivar Koppel	ivar.koppel@ut.ee	0000-0002-5617-4785
Ilja Livenson	ilja.livenson@ut.ee	0000-0002-4011-8367
Petri Nikunen	petri.nikunen@csc.fi	0000-0003-0759-6372
Ahti Saar	Ahti.Saar@ut.ee	0000-0003-0642-961X
Anders Sjöström	Anders.Sjostrom@lunarc.lu.se	0000-0003-2213-2138
Hjörleifur Sveinbjörnsson	hs@hi.is	0000-0002-4120-1234
John White	john.white@cern.ch	0000-0001-5614-0895